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Data management plan (DMP)

Planar Graph Classifier

PGC

Version	Effective date	Description of document/changes
1.0	2022-05-01	First version of DMP – created after completed project

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Start date	20.04.2022
End date	01.05.2022

List of acronyms

PGC	Planar Graph Classifier
DMP	data management plan
RDM	research data management
CSV	Comma Separated Values
CUDA	Compute Unified Device Architecture
cuDNN	CUDA Deep Neural Network

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Introduction

Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data

A DMP is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions.

For writing this DMP, we followed [the recommendations of Science Europe](#) as they reflect the guidelines agreed upon by the major funders in Europe.

To make our data FAIR, they generally will be treated according to the following criteria:

- We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata.
- We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.
- We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain by using the same file formats, schemas and vocabularies. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.
- We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published data sets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked.

Relevant Policies and Guidelines

- TU Wien Policy for Research Data Management: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Policy%20for%20Research%20Data%20Management.pdf>
- TU Wien Code of Conduct – Rules to Ensure Good Scientific Practice: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Code%20of%20Conduct%20%E2%80%93%20Rules%20to%20Ensure%20Good%20Scientific%20Practice.pdf>
- Directives and Regulations of the TU Wien Rectorate: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/directives-regulations/>
- TU Wien Data Protection: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/data-protection-at-tu-wien>
- European Commission's document on Ethics and Data Protection: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/5_h2020_ethics_and_data_protection.pdf

1. Data description

1a Lists of data sets that will be reused or produced

Produced data sets

dataset ID	name	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	gd_planar	archived data	G6	100 MB	no
P2	graph_img	images	png	1 GB	no
P3	class_info	structured text	csv	100 MB	no
P4	trained_model	configuration data	keras	100 MB	no
P5	set_split	structured text	csv	100 MB	no
P6	history.npy	other	numpy	100 MB	no
P7	evaluation.py	source code	csv	100 MB	no
P8	README.md	plain text	markdown	100 MB	no
P9	ego_facebook	archived data	tgz/edges	100 MB	no
P10	ego_twitch	archived data	zip/json	100 MB	no
P11	gd_rome	archived data	tgz/graphml	100 MB	no
P12	history.png	images	png	100 MB	no
P13	evaluation.csv	structured text	csv	100 MB	no

Reused data sets

dataset ID	name	type	format	DOI and license / source	contains sensitive data
R1	GD Planar	graph	G6	https://hog.grinvin.org/ListGraphs	no
R2	GD Rome	graph	graphml	http://graphdrawing.org/data.html	no
R3	Ego Facebook	graph	edges	https://snap.stanford.edu/data/ego-Facebook.html	no
R4	Ego Twitch	graph	json	https://snap.stanford.edu/data/twitch_ego_nets.html	no

1b Data generation and reuse

Data generation

The project is hosted on Bitbucket (<https://bitbucket.org/Remvipomed/planargraphclassifier>) and the archived input data was small enough to be included in the repository. The first step is to fully extract these datasets (P1, P9, P10, P11) into their respective location within the data structure. For the following steps, a Python 3.8 interpreter with the packages listed in requirements.txt is necessary. Running the preprocessing.py script will generate a large amount of graph images (P2) in png format, as well as class information associated with the image files (P3) as csv files. Based on the "is_planar" attribute, image files depicting planar graphs are categorized as class 1, while non-planar graphs are categorized as class 0. In order to create and train the neural network, the training.py script is run, which will first split the class_info into csv files for training and test set (P5). The training set is then used for loading input from graph_img in batches and handing it with the corresponding class info as target data to the fitting process of the keras model. After the training is done, the model is saved (P4) with its trained weights and custom configuration data from keras. Furthermore, a history of the measured loss and accuracy for each epoch during training is stored in a numpy file (P6). For the evaluation on the previously created test set (P5) the evaluation.py script needs to be run. This will load the trained_model and the graph_img data from the test set and use it to determine the final test accuracy. This will be saved together with the loss metric in the evaluation csv file (P13). Finally, the training progress can be visualized by running the plotting.py script, which will create a plot (P12) of loss and accuracy per epoch during training. Further information can be found in the project README (P8).

Data reuse

Several datasets with a wide variety of file formats were used as input data for this project. Two sets were chosen from the benchmark collection of the graph drawing community (R1, R2) with the list of graphs tagged as planar from R2 being especially useful in balancing the number of classes. For sets of larger graphs based on the amount of nodes and edges, two social networking sets (R3, R4) from the Stanford Large Network Dataset Collection were used.

2. Documentation and data quality

2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation

The filenames will follow the projects naming convention as defined in the README and include a timestamp of creation. Version control is automated.

We will not be using the domain specific metadata standards, however a metadata.xml file following the Dublin core will be provided at the project level in the doc folder.

A far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

2b Data quality control

Data quality checks will be done, e.g. checks of consistency of labels, logical errors in the data, data curation, and version control.

3. Storage and backup during research process

3a Storage and backup facilities

As the project is completed, there is no need anymore for backing up data in development. The long term storage of the repository will be dependent on Bitbucket, while the individual artefacts are archived on Zenodo.

3b Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies listed in the introduction of this document. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.

Access to the data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	writing	reading only
P2	writing	writing	reading only
P3	writing	writing	reading only
P4	writing	writing	reading only
P5	writing	writing	reading only
P6	writing	writing	reading only
P7	writing	writing	reading only
P8	writing	writing	reading only
P9	writing	writing	reading only
P10	writing	writing	reading only
P11	writing	writing	reading only
P12	writing	writing	reading only
P13	writing	writing	reading only

All incidents will be handled individually by the project leader team that is maintaining the affected service.

4. Legal and ethical requirements

4a Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.

4b Intellectual property rights and ownership

There are no legal restrictions on the processing and disclosure of our data.

4c Ethical issues

There is no involvement of humans or data relating to identifiable persons. Furthermore, there is no quantifiable expenditure of resources or the possibility of turning a profit. Therefore it is not expected for the project to be associated with any ethical issues. The research has not been reviewed yet by any ethics committee.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

5a Data publication and access conditions

The digital research data obtained will be published Open Access under a Creative Commons CC BY license, provided that there are no data protection concerns. Further data will be made available with restrictive access.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open		2022-05-01	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.6510067	
P2	Open		2022-05-01	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.6510093	
P3	Open		2022-05-01	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.6510113	
P4	Open		2022-05-01	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.6510117	
P5	Open		2022-05-01	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.6510126	
P6	Open		2022-05-01	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.6510128	
P7	Open		2022-05-01	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.6510163	
P8	Open		2022-05-01	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.6510150	
P9	Open		2022-05-01	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.6510073	
P10	Open		2022-05-01	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.6510076	
P11	Open		2022-05-01	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.6510069	
P12	Open		2022-05-01	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.6510154	
P13	Open		2022-05-01	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.6510163	

The repository used in this project described in the following paragraph.

Bitbucket is a web-based version control repository hosting service owned by Atlassian, for source code and development projects that use either Mercurial or Git revision control systems.
<https://bitbucket.org/>

The PGC project is found under <https://bitbucket.org/Remvipomed/planargraphclassifier>.

Specific tool or software is required to access and reuse the data: A git executable is necessary for cloning the repository and a standard file compression software such as 7-zip is needed to extract the archived input data. For running the python scripts, a Python 3.8 environment was set up with Anaconda3. The necessary libraries listed in the requirements.txt file were acquired with the package

managers pip and conda. Faster training with GPU support was accomplished with NVIDIA cuda capable hardware and the related drivers CUDA toolkit 11.2, cuDNN 8.1, as well as Microsoft Visual Studio 2019/2022.

Description of protocol to access restricted data:

5b Long-term preservation and reusability

dataset ID	location for long-term storage (min. 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P1	Zenodo	Members of the scientific community
P2	Zenodo	Members of the scientific community
P3	Zenodo	Members of the scientific community
P4	Zenodo	Members of the scientific community
P5	Zenodo	Members of the scientific community
P6	Zenodo	Members of the scientific community
P7	Zenodo	Members of the scientific community
P8	Zenodo	Members of the scientific community
P9	Zenodo	Members of the scientific community
P10	Zenodo	Members of the scientific community
P11	Zenodo	Members of the scientific community
P12	Zenodo	Members of the scientific community
P13	Zenodo	Members of the scientific community

Currently there are no plans to delete any of the artefacts related to PGC.

6. RDM responsibilities and resources

6a RDM-roles and responsibilities

The creator and project leader Matthias Hummel will handle all tasks related to the creation and management of data, as there are currently no other contributors.

6b Resources

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.